

SensApp

D1.1 Logo and webpage

Grant Agreement Number	829104
Project Name	Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach
Project Acronym	SensApp
Start date of the project	01/01/2019
End date of the project	31/12/2021
Work package producing the document	WP1 – Management and dissemination
Deliverable identifier	D1.1
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Contributors	All participants
Dissemination level	PU (public)
Author(s)	Veronica Vespini, CNR
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Delivery date	27/02/2019

1. Logo

The logo of SensApp project is presented below.

It contains the acronym of the project in red by assonance with the colour of blood. The acronym is surrounded by a celestial halo that accumulates in a drop under the last letter "P". This is related to the accumulation concept that is behind the technology proposed by the project. This acronym will identify the project in all of the communications related to the project, during the entire duration of the project and beyond the end of the project.

2. Webpage

We have set-up a dedicated webpage which provides a communication platform with public-facing pages, addressing the full range of stakeholders including the general public and schools, as well as with an area restricted to the consortium as described below. In order to increase the visibility of the project, each partner is encouraged to add a link to the project home page in their own institution website. The domain name for SensApp website is <https://sensapp.eu/>. The SensApp website itself has been implemented using Content Management System (CMS) WordPress 5.1. It's hosted by the Cloud Computing TurnKey Linux at "Area di Ricerca CNR Napoli 3" and is developed by **Gianluca Coda** and **Paolo Vanacore** (CNR). The public-facing pages are distributed according to the following menu:

- Home
- Project
- Team
- Technology
- Agenda
- News
- Publications
- Login

The page "Home" contains a highly recognizable visual identity of the project. Some pictures showing blood sampling and beta-Amyloid structure, the protein that is usually associated to the Alzheimer's disease, flow at the top of the page. Under the flowing pictures there is a general description of the project for the general public. We describe the state of the art for the diagnosis, the mission of the project and we give information about the funding source with a clear reference to the EU's H2020 programme and to the number of the Grant Agreement, with the EU emblem well in sight. **The page "Project"** contains the general information of the project including acronym, grant agreement id, list of partners and official links to the European FET Open website. **The page "Team"** contains the name and the pictures of the people involved in the project for each partner of the consortium. **The page "Technology"** illustrates in summary the technology that will be developed by SensApp, with a general description of the concept of accumulating low abundant biomarkers through the droplet-split-and-stack and with a comparison to the current methodologies (i.e. ELISA). **The page "Agenda"** shows the calendar of events (e.g. meetings, conferences, etc.) in order to keep the general public up-to-date on project progress. **The page "News"** gives information useful for the general public as well as for more sensor-oriented

students and researchers such as job opportunities, meetings open to public, etc. **The page “Publications”** contains information about the publications that will be produced by the consortium during the project and after the end of the project, including publications on peer reviewed journals, presentations at local and/or international conferences and industrial forums. **The page “Login”** allows the registered people belonging to the consortium to have access to project-related confidential documents concerning both the research-focused activities and the management and dissemination actions.

The website contains also the links to the profiles we have created for the project on the main **social media** used nowadays (Facebook; Twitter; Instagram; YouTube). The table below shows the list of the accounts created specifically for the project.

	References
Twitter	SensApp FET-OPEN Project @SensApp_H2020 https://twitter.com/SensApp_H2020
Facebook	SensApp Project https://www.facebook.com/SensApp-Project-1078043869041873/
Instagram	sensapp_h2020 SensApp Project H2020 https://www.instagram.com/sensapp_h2020/?hl=it
YouTube	SensApp Project https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCUKE9GtpuABUb4SruLuWSEw/featured?view_as=subscriber

The names we use for the social accounts clearly aim at stressing the project acronym and the affiliation of the project to the FET-Open action of the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. These social media accounts will provide real-time updates aimed particularly at reaching the general public as well as the younger generation of scientists. The Communications Manager of the project (**Veronica Vespini**, CNR) will take care of the requests from the consortium concerning both updates to the webpage and dissemination of project-related contents through the social media. The coordinator will encourage constantly the partners to contribute to the visibility of the project through their own personal and/or institutional accounts.

We have also created the following **email address** as the official contact of the project: sensapp.H2020@gmail.com. This is included into the webpage of the project. It will be managed by the Communications Manager and will represent the interface with the general public as well as the sensor- and/or clinician-oriented scientists who want to receive in-depth information about the project.

We have also produced the **first brochure of the project** and published in the “news” section of the webpage. It illustrates the framework of early diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease, the aim of the project, the general description of the technology developed by SensApp, the source of funding, the basic information about budget and consortium and the links to the social media accounts.

The following images show some **screenshots** of the SensApp webpage.

The web site was developed with a responsive design to make it usable on multiple devices (Fig. 1).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1 – Home page screenshots: (a) desktop view; (b) tablet view; (c) smartphone view.

Also, the SensApp website offers internal communications and file exchange services reserved to project partners (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – Menu items for reserved forum and cloud platform.

The forum (Fig. 3) allows consortium participants to exchange messages and engage discussions.

Fig. 3 - Discussion forum reserved to project partners

The cloud service is based on ownCloud platform¹ and allows the files exchange within the consortium (Fig. 4).

¹ <https://owncloud.org/>

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 - SensApp cloud platform: (a) logon to the reserved cloud platform; (b) cloud file management.

The impact of website communication is measured through some statistics such as unique visitors, clicks analysis and pages viewed (Fig. 5).

(a)

January 26, 2019 to Today

URL	Clicks
www.isasi.cnr.it	56
Twitter	36
sensapp.eu	22
facebook.com/SensApp-Project-1078043869041873/	20
www.b-phot.org	19
instagram.com/sensapp_h2020/	18
youtube.com/channel/UcUKE9GtpuABub4SruLuWSEw/	15
ec.europa.eu	13
www.jku.at	13
www.vttresearch.com	8
ginolis.com	5
www.irccsme.it	5
old.irccsneurolesiboninopulejo.it/?page_id=1997	4
www.turnkeylinux.org	3
cordis.europa.eu	2
en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HTTP_cookie	1

(b)

January 26, 2019 to Today		
Title		Views
Home		830
Team CNR		243
Home page / Archives		241
Technology		151
Team		150
Team VUB		106
Team VTT		101
Team Pulejo		88
Team JKU		80
Publications		71
Team Ginolis		69
News		69
KICK-OFF MEETING		45
Project Information		38
Agenda		29
Associate Researchers		25
Cookie Policy		24
Kick-off Meeting Media		12
Contact		11
The first brochure of SensApp project is now available		9
Activity		5
Members		2

(c)

Fig. 5 - Screens of website statistics: (a) visits over time; (b) click analysis; (c) post and page views statistics.

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